

BROMINATION OF COUMARINS. PART I. BROMINATION OF
7-HYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN, METHYL 7-HYDROXY-4-METHYL-
COUMARIN-6-CARBOXYLATE, 7-HYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN-
6-CARBOXYLIC ACID AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS

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7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid, methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate and their methyl ethers have been brominated with one molecule, two molecules and excess of bromine. It has been found that the first bromine atom in all cases enters the 3-position and the subsequent bromine atoms enter the benzene ring.

In the case of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin both the 3:6- and the 3:8-dibromocoumarins are obtained, the former being in preponderating yield. In the bromination of the 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin only the 3:6-dibromo derivative is formed, thus indicating that the 6-position is more reactive than the 8-position. Both the 3:6- and the 3:8-dibromo derivatives give the same 3:6:8-tribromo derivative on further bromination.

In the bromination of the hydroxy-ester, the hydroxy-acid and their methyl ethers, bromination with one molecule proceeds smoothly, the bromine atom entering the 3-position. The second bromine atom enters the 8-position but with difficulty. No dibromo product has been obtained in the direct bromination of the methoxy ester and the methoxy-acid.

In the bromination of coumarins it has been found by various workers that generally the first bromine atom enters the 3-position and the subsequent bromine atoms enter the benzene nucleus. It has been found, however, by Dey and Kutti (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1940, 6, 641) that in the bromination of 8-methoxycoumarin the first bromine atom enters the 5-position. Further, Fries and Lindemann (*Annalen*, 1914, 404, 53) have assigned the structure of 7-hydroxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin to the product obtained on bromination of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, since it was found to be different from 7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin obtained by the Pechmann condensation of 4-bromoresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate. In view of these results it was thought of interest to study the bromination of various coumarin derivatives, (i) to ascertain the reactivity of the different positions and (ii) to study the effect of substituents in the coumarin ring system on the course of bromination.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, $R=R'=H$) on bromination with one molecule of bromine gave the 3-bromocoumarin (II, $R=R'=H$), previously obtained by Fries and Nohren (*Ber.*, 1935, 58B, 1027) by bromination of the ethyl carbonate of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and subsequent hydrolysis of the bromo compound with alcoholic ammonium hydroxide to get the free hydroxy compound. Its methyl ether was found to be identical, on direct comparison, with 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=H$, $R'=Me$) obtained from the methyl ether of (I, $R=R'=H$) by bromination. The bromo compound has been previously obtained similarly by Limaye and Bhide (*Rasayanam*, 1938, 1, 136). Thus, the structure of 7-hydroxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin assigned to the bromination product of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin by Fries and Lindemann (*loc. cit.*) is found to be incorrect.

On bromination with two molecules of bromine, I ($R=R'=H$) gave a mixture of the 3:6-dibromo-(II, $R=Br$, $R'=H$) and the 3:8-dibromocoumarin (III, $R=R'=H$). The methyl ethers were prepared and on hydrolysis they gave bromocoumarilic acid derivatives (IV, $R=Br$, $R'=Me$, $R''=H$ and IV, $R=H$, $R''=Me$, $R'=Br$ respectively), thus indicating that one bromine atom in both the compounds is in the 3-position. One of the methyl ethers was found to be identical with the only dibromo compound obtained in the bromination of 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin with two molecules of bromine. The structure of 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=Br$, $R'=Me$) was assigned to this product because it was found to be identical with the dibromo compound obtained on bromination of 7-methoxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin which was prepared according to Chakravarti and Mukerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 725) from 4-bromoresorcinol. The other compound was therefore 7-methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (III, $R=H$, $R'=Me$). 7-Methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin has been previously obtained by Limaye and Bhide (*loc. cit.*) but they did not assign a definite constitution to this product.

The coumarin I ($R=R'=H$) with excess of liquid bromine gave the 3:6:8-tribromo compound (III, $R=Br$, $R'=H$). The methyl ether of this was found to be identical with the 3:6:8-tribromocoumarin (III, $R=Br$, $R'=Me$) obtained by the bromination of the methyl ether of I ($R=R'=H$).

Methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$), prepared according to Shah *et. al.* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 717), on bromination with one molecule of bromine gave the 3-bromocoumarin (II, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$). Its methyl ether was found to be identical with the bromocoumarin obtained by the bromination of the methyl ether of I ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) with one molecule of bromine.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (I, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) (Shah *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) on bromination with one molecule of bromine gave the 3-bromo-acid, identical with the product obtained on hydrolysis of the monobromo ester (II, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) with cold alkali. The bromo-acid could not be methylated.

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (I, $R=COOH$, $R'=Me$) which could not be obtained by the methylation of the corresponding hydroxy-acid, was obtained by the hydrolysis of the methoxy ester I ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$). This on bromination with

one molecule of bromine gave the 3-bromo-acid, identical with the product obtained on hydrolysis of the monobromo ester II ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$) with cold alkali.

The ester (I, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) on bromination with excess of liquid bromine gave the 3:8-dibromo compound (III, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) which was methylated to III ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$). This could not, however, be obtained by the direct bromination of the methoxy ester I ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$). The acid (I, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) on bromination with excess of liquid bromine gave the 3:8-dibromo compound III ($R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) which was identical with the product obtained on hydrolysis of the dibromo ester III ($R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) with cold alkali. The methoxy-dibromo ester (III, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$) on hydrolysis with cold alkali gave the methoxy-dibromo acid III ($R=CO_2H$, $R'=Me$). This could not, however, be obtained by the direct bromination of the acid (I, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=Me$).

The presence of the bromine atom in the 3-position has been shown by hydrolysis of the bromo-esters to the coumarilic acid derivatives. In the case of the dibromo compounds, the other bromine atom can only enter the 8-position which is *ortho* to the hydroxyl group and therefore the structure of 3:8-dibromocoumarin is assigned to the dibromo products.

No tribromo derivative could be obtained on bromination of the ester (I, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=H$) and the acid (I, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) with excess of bromine under different conditions e.g. in presence of sodium acetate, in presence of iron wire, by refluxing with bromine in acetic acid, and so on.

Attempts to decarboxylate the monobromo acid (II, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) and the dibromo acid (III, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=H$) by heating in a sealed tube with water, with dilute hydrochloric acid and by heating with quinoline and copper powder did not succeed.

Attempts to prepare methyl 7-methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (III, $R=CO_2Me$, $R'=Me$) and 7-methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (III, $R=CO_2H$, $R'=Me$) by the bromination of methyl 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate and the corresponding acid were made under different conditions but they did not succeed, either demethylation or hydrolysis of the ester took place.

It has been found that the coumarilic acids are best obtained from the methoxybromocoumarins. The corresponding hydroxybromocoumarins generally give pasty products on hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=R'=H$).—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g.), prepared according to Pechmann and Duisberg (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2122), was dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) by heating and bromine (1.6 g., 1 mol.) in acetic acid (16 c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool, when needles of the bromo compound separated out. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 213-15°. (Found: Br, 31.3. $C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.4 per cent). Fries and Nohren (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 213°. It gives a blue fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and forms yellow alkali salts whose dilute solutions show a bluish green fluorescence.

The methyl ether, m.p. 147°, obtained by refluxing the compound with methyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate, was found to be identical, on direct comparison, with 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin prepared according to Limaye and Bhide (*loc. cit.*).

7-Hydroxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, R=Br, R'=H) and *7-Hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin* (III, R=R'=H).—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) by heating and bromine (3.2 g., 2 mols.) in acetic acid (32 c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The reaction mixture was then heated on a boiling water-bath for two hours when a solid separated out which was filtered off on cooling, m.p. 240°-260°. This was refluxed with acetic acid (50 c.c.) for 15 minutes when a part of it dissolved. The solution was filtered while hot and the filtrate allowed to cool. This was worked up as given below. The residue was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless, shining, elongated plates, m.p. 274-76°, yield 0.5 g. This is 7-hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin. (Found: Br, 47.7. $C_{10}H_6O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 47.9 per cent).

The crystals which separated out from the filtrate (from above) on cooling were recrystallised from acetic acid in small white needles, m.p. 246-48°, yield 1 g. This is 7-hydroxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin. (Found: Br, 47.5. $C_{10}H_6O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 47.9 per cent).

Both the compounds form yellow salts with alkalis, dilute solutions of which show a faint bluish green fluorescence.

Both the above compounds were obtained on further bromination of 7-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin. They also gave 7-hydroxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin on further bromination.

7-Methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (III, R=H, R'=Me) was prepared by methylation of 7-hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin with methyl iodide as usual. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 235°. (Found: Br, 45.7. $C_{11}H_8O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 46.0 per cent).

7-Methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, R=Br, R'=Me), prepared by methylating 7-hydroxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin with methyl iodide as usual, gave m.p. 240°. Mixed melting point with the dibromo compound obtained from 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin according to Limaye and Bhide (*loc. cit.*) was not lowered. The constitution of this compound was proved by synthesis from 4-bromoresorcinol as follows.

4-Bromoresorcinol was prepared according to the method of Sandin and McKee ("Organic Syntheses", 1937, Vol. XVII, pp. 23-24) and condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid (Chakravarti and Mukerjee, *loc. cit.*) to get 7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin. This was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali (Chakravarti and Mukerjee, *loc. cit.*) when 7-methoxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin resulted. This was brominated with one molecule of bromine in acetic acid to get 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin.

6-Methoxy-7-bromo-3-methylcoumarinic Acid (IV, R=H, R'=Me, R''=Br).—7-Methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1N, 20 c.c.) for 2 hours. It was then cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid.

The precipitated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in small white prisms, m.p. 252° (decomp.), yield 0.4 g. (Found: Br, 28.3. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 28.1 per cent). It gives a blue coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid on warming.

6-Methoxy-5-bromo-4-methylcoumarilic acid (IV, R=Br, R'=Me, R''=H).—7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 20 c.c.) for two hours. The solution was then cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in small white needles, m.p. 256° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. Limaye and Bhide (*loc. cit.*) give the same melting point.

7-Hydroxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin (III, R=Br, R'=H).—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2 g.) was placed in a flask and liquid bromine (3 c.c., excess) added. There was a copious evolution of hydrogen bromide fumes. The mixture was then kept overnight. The residual solid was treated with a strong solution of sodium bisulphite to remove the excess of bromine. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in small, colorless, shining plates, m.p. 250-52, yield 2.5 g. (Found: Br, 58.4. $C_{10}H_7O_3Br_3$ requires Br, 58.1 per cent). It forms yellow alkali salts, dilute solutions of which give a faint bluish green fluorescence.

This compound was also obtained when 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was brominated with one molecule of bromine in presence of sodium acetate and by further bromination of the 3:6- and 3:8-dibromocoumarins.

7-Methoxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin (III, R=Br, R'=Me).—7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (2 g.) was gently refluxed on a water-bath with liquid bromine (5 c.c., excess) for 4 hours. The bromine was then allowed to evaporate and the residual solid was treated with a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide to remove the demethylated product. The insoluble product was then filtered and washed several times with water to remove the adhering sodium salt of the demethylated product and then crystallised from acetic acid in colorless, cubic plates, m.p. 196-98°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: Br, 56.5. $C_{11}H_7O_3Br_3$ requires Br, 56.2 per cent). Mixed melting point with 7-methoxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin, obtained by methylation of 7-hydroxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin, was not depressed.

6-Methoxy-5:7-dibromo-3-methylcoumarilic Acid (IV, R=R''=Br, R'=Me).—7-Methoxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1*N*, 20 c.c.) for two hours. The resulting solution was cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in small, white cubes, m.p. 268° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. (Found: Br, 43.7. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 44.0 per cent). It gives a blue coloration on warming with sulphuric acid.

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (I, R=CO₂H, R'=Me).—Methyl 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (10 g.), prepared according to Shah *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), was heated on a boiling water-bath with sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 100 c.c.) for half an hour when the ester went into solution completely. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in small needles, m.p. 268-70° (decomp.), yield 6 g. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 4.3. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.3 per cent).

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (II, R=CO₂Me, R'=H).—Methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (2.34 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) by heating and bromine (1.6 g., 1 mol.) dissolved in acetic acid (16 c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The reaction mixture was kept overnight when crystals of the monobromo compound separated out. Crystals from acetic acid, m.p. 196-98°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: Br, 25.3. C₁₂H₉O₅Br requires Br, 25.6 per cent).

This compound was methylated with methyl iodide in the usual manner and the methyl ether found to be identical, on direct comparison, with methyl 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (described below).

Methyl 7-Methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (II, R=CO₂Me, R=Me).—Methyl 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (2.48 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) by heating and bromine (1.6 g., 1 mol.) in acetic acid (16 c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The crystals of the monobromo compound obtained on keeping the reaction mixture overnight were crystallised from acetic acid in silky, white needles, m.p. 208-10°, yield 2.4 g. (Found: Br, 24.8. C₁₃H₁₁O₅Br requires Br, 24.5 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-methyl-5-carboxylcoumarilic Acid (IV, R=CO₂H, R=Me, R'=H).—Methyl 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (1g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1N, 20 c.c.) for two hours on a wire gauze. The solution was then cooled, filtered and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in small, white needles, m.p. 288° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 57.4; H, 4.2. C₁₂H₁₀O₆ requires C, 57.6; H, 4.0 per cent). It gives a violet coloration when warmed with concentrated sulphuric acid.

7-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (II, R=CO₂H, R'=H).—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (2.2 g.) was suspended in hot acetic acid (20c.c.) and bromine (1.6 g., 1mol.) in acetic acid (16c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot suspension, when the acid gradually went into solution. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and the solid which separated out was crystallised from dilute alcohol in small, colorless needles, m.p. 260° (decomp.), yield 1.7g. (Found: Br, 26.9. C₁₁H₇O₅Br requires Br, 26.8 per cent).

This acid was also obtained when methyl 7-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate was hydrolysed by keeping with 5% alkali for 40 hours at room temperature.

7-Methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (II, R=CO₂H, R'=Me).—7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (2.34 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (50c.c.) and bromine (1.6 g., 1mol.) in acetic acid (16c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The reaction mixture was then heated on a boiling water-bath for an hour and then allowed to stand overnight. The solid which separated out was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 263-65° (decomp.), yield 2.4 g. (Found: Br, 25.4. C₁₂H₉O₅Br requires Br, 25.6 per cent).

This acid was also obtained by hydrolysing methyl 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate with dilute alkali at room temperature.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (III, R=CO₂Me, R'=H).—Methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (2 g.) was placed in a flask and liquid bromine (5c.c., excess) added gradually to it. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The residual solid after treatment with sodium bisulphite solution was crystallised from acetic acid in tiny, white needles, m.p. 240-42°, yield 2.6 g. (Found : Br, 40.7. C₁₃H₈O₅Br₂ requires Br, 40.8 per cent).

The *methyl ether* was prepared by refluxing it in acetone solution with methyl iodide in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate for 20 hours. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 184°-86. (Found : Br, 39.6. C₁₃H₁₀O₅Br₂ requires Br, 39.4 per cent).

6-Methoxy-7-bromo-3-methyl-5-carboxylcoumarilic Acid (IV, R=CO₂H, R'=Me, R''=Br).—Methyl 7-methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1N, 20 c.c.) for 2 hours. The solid obtained on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid in small, white cubes, m.p. 278° (decomp.). (Found : Br, 24.6. C₁₂H₉O₆Br requires Br, 24.3 per cent). It gives a violet coloration when warmed with concentrated sulphuric acid.

7-Hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (III, R=CO₂H, R'=H).—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (2.2 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and bromine (3.2g., 2mols.) in acetic acid (32c.c.) added. The reaction mixture was then gently refluxed on a wire gauze for two hours. The solid which separated on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid in small, white needles, m.p. 286° (decomp.), yield 2.3 g. (Found: Br, 42.7. C₁₁H₈O₅Br₂ requires Br, 42.3 per cent).

7-Methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (III, R=CO₂H, R'=Me).—Methyl 7-methoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (0.5 g.) was kept with sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 20c.c.) for 40 hours when the ester went into solution. The solution was filtered and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in shining, white needles, m.p. 248°-50° (decomp.). (Found : Br, 40.5. C₁₂H₈O₆Br₂ requires Br, 40.8 per cent).

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. R. C. Shah for his kind interest in the work.

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Received April 21, 1949.